

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part II. Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin

Jagdish N. Srivastava and D. N. Chaudhury

The synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III) has been effected.

In Part I of this series, the synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin has been reported (Banerjee and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, in press). The present communication deals with the synthesis of the isomeric 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III). 4,5-Dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol (II), the key compound for the synthesis of the dihydroisocoumarin (III), was prepared by two routes. Nitration of methyl homoveratrate ("Org. Syn.", 1943, Coll. Vol., II, p. 333) at 0° yielded almost exclusively methyl-6-nitrohomoveratrate (I: R=CH₂COOMe), the orientation of which was established by comparison with an authentic specimen prepared from 6-nitrohomoveratric acid (I:R=CH₂COOH) (Hahn and Schulz, *Ber.*, 1939, **72**, 1312) with an excess of ethereal diazomethane. In the synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (*loc. cit.*), it has been shown that LiAlH₄ reduction of methyl 2-nitrohomoveratrate afforded a mixture of 2,3,2',3'-tetramethoxy-6,6'-dihydroxyethylazobenzene and 2-nitrohomoveratryl alcohol, which as such or separately, when reduced with sodium dithionite, gave 3,4-dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol. Accordingly, adopting the same procedure methyl 6-nitrohomoveratrate (I: R=CH₂COOMe) was reduced successively with LiAlH₄ and sodium dithionite to yield 4,5-dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol (II), isolated as its hydrochloride.

In an alternative procedure, homoveratryl alcohol (Howell and Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4252) on nitration at 0° gave 6-nitrohomoveratryl alcohol (I:R=CH₂CH₂OH) which was reduced with sodium dithionite to 4,5-dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol (II); this transformation incidentally proved the orientation of the nitro-alcohol (I: R=CH₂CH₂OH).

Finally, diazotisation of (II), its conversion into the nitrile (which was not purified), and subsequent alkaline hydrolysis, followed by acidification, gave 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III).

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 6-Nitrohomoveratrate (I: R=CH₂COOMe).—Methyl homoveratrate (5 g.) was added portionwise to HNO₃ (25 c.c., *d* 1.42) with constant stirring; the temperature during addition was not allowed to rise above 0°. The reaction mixture was left at 10° for an hour and then poured into ice-water (250 c.c.). The precipitate was filtered after an hour, washed thoroughly with water, and recrystallised from methanol as yellow needles (4.5 g.), m.p. 116-17°. (Found: C, 51.5; H, 5.2. C₁₁H₁₃O₆N requires C, 51.76; H, 5.09%).

6-Nitrohomoveratryl Alcohol (I: R=CH₂CH₂OH).—Homoveratryl alcohol (1.6 g.) was added in portions to HNO₃ (9 c.c., *d* 1.42) with constant stirring, the temperature being maintained at 0°. The reaction mixture after being kept at 5° for half an hour was poured into ice-water (200 c.c.) when a yellow precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with ice-cold water, and dried in a desiccator. Repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) furnished irregular prisms, m.p. 107°, yield 0.7g. (Found: C, 52.2; H, 5.6. C₁₀H₁₃O₅N requires C, 52.8; H, 5.7%).

4,5-Dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl Alcohol (II): *Method (a)*.—A solution of methyl 6-nitrohomoveratrate (I: R=CH₂COOMe) (1.5 g.) in dry THF (30 c.c.) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of LiAlH₄ (0.6 g.) in dry THF (25 c.c.), cooled to -15°, and left overnight at room temperature. Unchanged LiAlH₄ and the complex were decomposed by careful portionwise addition of ice-water (10 c.c.) followed by 2*N*-H₂SO₄ (40 c.c.). It was extracted with ether (3 × 50 c.c.). The combined ether extract was dried (K₂CO₃) and evaporated to a dark red solid which was dissolved in methanol (25 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.). Sodium dithionite (2 g.) was added in portions when the dark red colour was immediately discharged to a pale yellow solution and it was refluxed on a water bath for half an hour. After distilling most of the methanol, the solution was repeatedly extracted with chloroform (3 × 40 c.c.), the yellow chloroform solution extracted with 56% HCl (2 × 25 c.c.), and separated. The acid solution was cooled, mixed with chloroform (25 c.c.), basified carefully with ammonia (*d* 0.88), and vigorously shaken. The chloroform layer was separated and the aqueous layer further extracted with chloroform (2 × 25 c.c.). The combined chloroform extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent distilled to yield the amino-alcohol (II) as a red oil which soon solidified to yellow needles, m.p. 84-86°. As it rapidly underwent oxidation in air, it was immediately taken up in dry ether (25 c.c.), chilled to -15°, and dry hydrogen chloride bubbled through when the *amine hydrochloride* (0.375 g.) separated as dark needles. After recrystallisation from methanol-ether it was further purified by sublimation *in vacuo* (bath temp. 160°/0.1 mm) as white needles, m.p. 197-98°. (Found: C, 51.4; H, 6.2. C₁₀H₁₆O₃NCl requires C, 51.3; H, 6.4%).

Method (b).—6-Nitrohomoveratryl alcohol (I: R=CH₂CH₂OH) (1 g.) in methanol (25 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.) was refluxed with sodium dithionite (3.5 g.) for half hour. During this period water (10 c.c.) was added in instalments to dissolve the sodium dithionite, when a clear solution was obtained. It was cooled, methanol distilled, and the aqueous solution extracted with chloroform (3 × 15 c.c.). The chloroform solution was treated as in method (a) to isolate the amino-alcohol (II) as its *hydrochloride* (0.6 g.), m.p. 197-98°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained by method (a).

* All m.p.'s are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Dr. Gore, Dept. of Chemical Technology, University of Bombay.

3,4-Dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III).—The hydrochloride of (II) (0.380 g.) in HCl (0.38 c.c., *d*l.16) and water (9 c.c.) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.12 g.) in water (1 c.c.) at 0-2°. After neutralisation with sodium carbonate, the diazonium solution was added to a solution of KCN (0.380 g.), nickel chloride (0.300 g.) and anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.1g.) in water (10 c.c.) at 15° with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours at 15° and then heated to 75° for 45 minutes. The solution was cooled, extracted with ether (4 × 20 c.c.), the combined ether extract was dried (Na₂SO₄), and the ether distilled to give a red gum. The gum was refluxed with aqueous KOH (20 c.c., 10%) for 4 hours, cooled, and acidified with HCl (conc.) (Congo red). The solution was filtered and extracted with chloroform (3 × 25 c.c.), the extract dried (Na₂SO₄), and the solvent evaporated to give a gum which solidified on standing overnight to yellow needles. It was sublimed *in vacuo* (bath temp. 120-25°/0.1 mm) to yield a white solid, m.p. 134-36°. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) afforded 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin as colorless needles (0.21 g.), m.p. 140-41°. (Found: C, 63.0; H, 5.5. C₁₁H₁₂O₄ requires C, 63.4; H, 5.7%). I. R. in CHCl₃: 5.88μ (conjugated δ-lactone).

The authors wish to thank Dr. Tapan K. Mukherjee, Retina Foundation, Boston 14, Mass., U.S.A., for the I. R. data and the U. G. C. for the award of a research scholarship to one of them (J. N. S.).